

Simulating Plankton - getting it right in the era of Digital Twins of The Ocean

Project introduction and executive discussion

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Citing this work

Flynn KJ (2024) *Simulating Plankton - getting it right in the era of Digital Twins of The Ocean; projection introduction and executive discussion*. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10953377>

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Funder

This work was funded by UKRI Natural Environment Research Council (NE/X010783/1; *Simulating Plankton - getting it right in the era of Digital Twins of The Ocean*), under the direction of the author.

Acknowledgements

The author wishes to thank the following for their comments on earlier versions of aspects of this report:

C Bowler (IBENS, France), D Caron (USC, USA), MW Lomas (Bigelow USA), C Luca (Southampton, UK), B Rost (AWI, Germany).

Special thanks are extended to Evelyn Sherr (Oregon, USA) for extensive proof reading and suggestions.

Executive Summary

This work describes an overview of, and the overarching outcomes from, a project funded by the NERC (UK) during 2023, with the aim of facilitating the construction of the next generation of plankton simulation models by engaging with experts in real plankton physiology and ecology. Target audiences include those involved in designing and developing plankton digital twins. These are simulation platforms designed specifically for a variety of end-users, not solely for modellers. Such platforms must therefore perform, at all levels, to the expectations of experts in the real world. Over 30 experts, covering plankton from viruses to krill, contributed to various facets of the project. They were selected specifically for their empirical interests; modellers per se were not included.

This work introduces the challenges in building plankton digital twins, and also the components of the project.

Information within the project will help empiricists better understand the usefulness and limitations of plankton models in the extant literature (to gauge what constitutes a model that is closer to providing a simulation rather than a theoretical exploration) and also what sorts of data (numeric and phenomenological) modellers need from empiricists. Modellers of plankton will also be better informed by this project, on what to include in their creations to ensure that they are better able to provide simulations.

Key outcomes from the 4 tasks comprising the project are:

1. Empiricists have low levels of confidence in the conceptual design and simulations produced by extant plankton models. They expect inclusion of meaningful complexity in both the descriptions of the planktonic organisms and the food webs. They are accepting of 'failure' because that points the way to future developments and enhancement of understanding. Failings attributed to simplicity are not acceptable. Digital twin plankton models will inevitably be more complex than extant models.
2. Faced with trade-offs in complexity of organism description and food web structure, empiricists are more likely to require the latter. However, understanding that facets of ecology (such as resource selection) are controlled by details of the organism description, empiricists require a balance between physiological detail of some organisms and inclusion of more types. This points to a desire by empiricists to want access to a flexible modelling platform in which they can experiment with model complexity to test options exploiting their expert validation skills.
3. Numeric data availability for the support of plankton modelling is poor, both with respect to quality (measurements in appropriate units) and quantity (across different organisms and conditions). The construction of a database of literature selected by empiricists flags a need for those empiricists themselves to be involved in model construction and testing, to provide expert witness validation.
4. Interest in first generation plankton digital twins is in platforms describing significant levels of detail (organism physiology, food web linkage, multi-stressors) in 0D or 1D (depth), over relatively short periods of time (ca. week-month). Such simulation-based, digital-twin laboratories or mesocosms would provide useful platforms for testing plankton models and exploring ecological questions. More importantly, these platforms would provide an educational interface between empiricists and modellers to the benefit of all.

The actual construction of digital twin models is beyond the scope of this work, and it will take many years for the more advanced digital twins to become ready for deployment. However, it is hoped that more simple digital twins (supporting laboratory and mesocosm scale scenarios) will become available within the next few years.

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Glossary

Terms in italics are explained elsewhere in the glossary

Autecology – Ecological study of an individual organism (species or group); may also referred to as ecophysiology. (Cf. *Synecology*)

Closure term – A catch-all term added to the uppermost trophic level described in a model to account for all losses applied to that level. For example, a closure term on *metazoan-zooplankton* would, amongst other things, account for predation by fish and age-related mortality.

Constant – A parameter in a model that is not changed during the simulation. Rarely are such parameters true constants in nature.

Decision Support Tool (DST) – A framework, often supported by outputs from a computer programme, to optimise a management or other operational strategy. DSTs may be as simple as a look-up table or decision tree, or as complex as a *digital twin* enabling near-real-time analysis of options.

(de)repression – A biological control mechanism, usually involving feedback, through which physiological (biochemical, behavioural) processes are modulated by being gradually enabled (repressed) or disabled (de-repressed).

Digital Twin (DT) – A digital representation of an intended or actual real-world physical product, system, or process (a physical twin) that serves as the effectively indistinguishable digital counterpart of it for practical purposes, such as simulation, integration, testing, monitoring, and maintenance. DTs range from being static (e.g., geological structure) through to highly dynamic (e.g., aircraft in flight). Dynamic versions are often associated explicitly or implicitly with a *Decision Support Tool* to guide an intervention. Dynamics DTs may be differentiated from a *simulation model* by the presence of an interface to enable the user (who may be a non-specialist, and invariably not the originator of the model) to interact with the model and to explore features beyond the data originally used in model validation in a predictive or ‘what-if?’ mode, perhaps in real time.

Dysfunctionality – Behavioural trait of a model that is contrary to expectation, as distinct from simply being absent through simplification (as per Flynn 2005b, 2010).

Dunning-Kruger effect – Cognitive bias that leads to an overestimation of one’s ability, and associated with an inability to recognise failings and mistakes.

Empirical – Based on observation (e.g., field, laboratory) rather than through theory or logic. Empirical data may be subject to subsequent transformations or manipulations based upon theory or logic, but the data are not synthetic, as are those generated by a *model*.

Expert Witness Validation (EWV) – A means to validate the performance of a numeric model by exploiting a form of *Turing test*, asking of experts with a phenomenological understanding in the real world system, ‘does this model output so-closely resemble reality that you could be fooled by it?’ EWV minimises the risks of over-fitting by explicitly considering the full breadth of phenomenological understanding. (see *phenomenological data*)

Grain – Level of detail; fine grain for *Systems Biology* models may include a description of individual biochemical processes, while coarse grain may refer physiological processes modulated through reference to elemental stoichiometry.

Metazoan-zooplankton – Zooplankton with multi-cellular bodies, contrasting with the *protistan-zooplankton*. Often with several distinct ontogenic stages.

Microalgae - Generic descriptor of any microbe capable of photosynthesis (containing chlorophyll), and thus may include any or all *phytoplankton* and *mixoplankton*. As these organisms are almost certainly all capable of *osmotrophy*, they are also all mixotrophic through photo-osmo-trophy.

Microzooplankton – Traditional term to describe microbial zooplankton (of any size) and/or micro-sized (i.e., 0.02-0.2mm) zooplankton. The term may include any or all *protistan-zooplankton*, *mixoplankton*, and potentially smaller *metazoan-zooplankton* and/or their juvenile stages.

Mixoplankton - Protist plankton that combine phototrophy and *phagotrophy*. Many have formally been termed *phytoplankton*, and some have been termed as *microzooplankton* or *protistan-zooplankton*. They almost certainly all also engage in *osmotrophy*. Their phototrophic capability may be acquired from their prey (non-constitutive mixoplankton; these have traditionally been confused with *protistan-zooplankton*) or innate (constitutive mixoplankton; these have traditionally been confused with *phytoplankton*) (see Mitra et al. 2016).

Mixotroph – Traditionally a mode of nutrition through which C and energy are acquired through both autotrophy (typically photosynthesis) and heterotrophy (as *osmotrophy* and/or *phagotrophy*). Modern usage sees the role of heterotrophy in mixotrophy as providing nutrients in addition to C as organic-linked N, P, Fe etc. *Phytoplankton* are all potentially mixotrophic through phototrophy + *osmotrophy*. Mixoplankton are mixotrophic through phototrophy+*phagotrophy* (and also + *osmotrophy*).

Model – A simplification of reality, ranging from abstract to physical, static to dynamic, including mathematical constructs from statistical fits to *numeric models* that may be hypothetical, through to simulations and *Digital Twins*. Data generated by a mathematical model are synthetic rather than *empirical*.

Numeric model – A mathematical model that uses a complex series of equations, often involving differential calculus to described events changing over time, as used to provide *simulations*.

'omics – Molecular biological suffix (e.g., genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics) of terms for biological molecules that characterize organismal structures and functions ranging from genes, transcripts, proteins (especially enzymes), and metabolites.

Operational envelope – the boundaries of conditions in which a *simulation model* can be safely operated (i.e., outside of this envelope, the model may provide an output that conforms to the definition of a *simulation*).

Osmotrophy – Nutrition involving the uptake of dissolved organics, often for nutrients (N, P, Fe, etc.) as well as for C.

Over-fitting – A consequence of fitting or *tuning* a model (especially a statistical model) that, because it describes a particular data set too closely, is then unable to reproduce the general case.

Phagotrophy – Technically a mode of nutrition involving the engulfment of particulate organics (often organisms) into the protist cell, but more commonly to include other modes of feeding by protists such as the use of a peduncle (feeding straw), traps, extracellular digestion, etc.

Phenomenological data - Data in the form of information (e.g., natural history) held by someone (or perhaps something) who has observed the behaviour of a system, has formed a conceptual understanding, and thus has an appreciation of how a similar system may behave. (see *Expert Witness Validation*)

Phytoplankton – Plankton (prokaryote and/or eukaryote) that engage in phototrophy, and most likely also *osmotrophy* (but not *phagotrophy* – Cf. *mixoplankton*), and are thus potentially *mixotrophs*.

- Plankton functional type (PFT)** – a label given to a collection of plankton that share similar traits. Those traits should be ecophysiological, and not biogeochemical; biogeochemistry is an emergent property of interactions between ecology and the environment.
- Protistan-zooplankton** – protists that engage in *phagotrophy* but not phototrophy (Cf. *mixoplankton*); they may also engage in *osmotrophy*.
- Simulation (model)** – The output of a *numeric model* that provide an approximation of a real world process changing over time, at least over the conditions under which it was *validated*. (cf. *Digital Twin*)
- State variable** – A parameter with history, such as concentration or abundance. The value of state variables usually change over time as the *simulation* progresses. In multi-dimensional models (i.e., models describing over spatial scales), at each iteration the state variable for any given spatial location may also share a proportion of its contents (i.e., its value) with the state variables in adjacent locations.
- Stress** – An event eliciting an additional expenditure of energy and/or allocation of resources to mitigate against the (usually negative) impact on the organism’s physiology. The stress need not result in a deterioration in growth rate, though it likely results in a deterioration in the scope for growth such that multiple stressors (each alone not affecting the growth rate) collectively results in a decreased growth rate.
- Synecology** – Ecological study of whole communities; often just termed ecology. (Cf. *autecology*)
- Systems biology** – Computational analysis and modelling of complex biological interactions using a holistic approach (e.g., with explicit inclusion of (*de*)*repression* feedbacks), rather than the traditional reductionist approach of modelling in which the drive for simplification is a dominant feature.
- System dynamics** – A modelling approach characterised by explicit inclusion of active feed-back and feed-forward interactions especially developed for or suited to simulating complex numeric data-poor situations.
- Technology Readiness Level (TRL)** – A grading of maturity in technology development, ranging from TRL1 (basic research), via TRL5 (technology development/demonstration) to TRL9 (mature and fully operational).
- TEP** – Transparent Exopolymer Particles; a form of organics particles (extracellular acidic polysaccharides), that can accumulate and help form marine snow and foams.
- Timestep** – the period of simulation time over which a *numeric model* (such as a *simulation* supporting a *Digital Twin*) integrates processes. Also known as the integration step size.
- Trait** – Characteristic; in the context of *simulation modelling* often referred to as a ‘functional trait’, rather than one that may be considered as cosmetic.
- Tuning** – Optimising the fit of (minimising differences between) model output and external (usually real world) data series by the modification of *constants* present in the model equations. Cf. *validation*. May be termed ‘optimisation’.
- Turing test** – A test of a machine’s (computer programme’s) ability to exhibit a level of intelligent behaviour similar to, and thus indistinguishable from, that of a human (Turing 1950). Cf. *Expert Witness Validation*.
- Validation** – A means of determining the veracity of a model output against external (usually *empirical* numeric) data series independent from those data used for *tuning* or optimisation. Often in biological and ecological science there are very few data available once those used for tuning have been excluded. See also *Expert Witness Validation*.

1. Introduction – project scope

A simulation is a computer-rendered representation of a reality as it changes over time. Digital twins (DT) are simulation models with which the end-user (often a non-modeller) can readily interface, ideally doing so in real time during the simulation. An example of a DT is a flight simulator (see **Appendix 1**), where the user ‘flies’ an aircraft. The representation may be generic (propeller vs jet propelled, aircraft vs helicopter) or very specific (Airbus 320 vs Concorde). Such a simulation follows (reproduces) certain rules of reality, and the knowledgeable user will readily recognise if the simulation is not actually believable and thus cannot provide an acceptable DT experience.

A biology-facing DT should enable the user to explore and experiment with the biological system in a similar way to studying an empirical (real) operating system, but to be able to do so much quicker and efficiently. Explorations can also be undertaken that would be logistically or ethically impossible in reality.

Here we consider open water plankton as the target subject (acknowledging that there are direct and indirect connections with the benthos, and also with the activities of non-planktonic higher trophic levels in the water column). Plankton are of global importance in marine waters and there are also important freshwater plankton species which this work relates to.

A plankton DT may have uses in education, research, management, etc., with applications ranging from cultures growing in a flask, containing just 1 or a few plankton species, all the way through to ocean realms. There are several steps in building such a platform (Flynn et al. 2022), but none are more important than ensuring that the simulation engine for plankton that lays at the heart of the DT platform is behaving as it should throughout the operational envelope in which the end user may run it. This need represents an important point of deviation from traditional usage of plankton models. Traditionally the users of models are also the developers; the model is built to fulfil a specific task and should not be used outside of that limited operational envelope. A plankton DT model may be operated in any plausible situation, by users other than the developers, and the behaviour of each plankton component needs to align with that expected of real organisms.

A critical requirement is to establish what a DT for different plankton types may be expected to do, and not to do. Thus, if an expert in the ecology of the real organisms saw an output from the plankton DT, or experimented with the DT, could they be fooled into believing it was real, or is the simulated behaviour at too much variance with plausible real behaviour? The conduct of such tests comprises ‘expert witness validation’, as a form of Turing test. This phenomenological validation augments the traditional modellers tools of conducting numeric validation, and is required here because plankton science in general lacks a suitable array of empirical data with which to conduct such a numeric analysis (Flynn et al. 2022, 2024b).

Although, from the above, this project could be seen as one dominated by autecology, in reality the growth and responses of each organisms relates to those of others, and thence to plankton ecology in general. In addition, while explicitly directed at the development of digital twins, the work is equally (arguably more) important in considering the formulation of models intended to simulate events of important socio-economic consequence, such as climate change predictions.

This work is not directed at giving modellers what they think they want (such as, maximum growth rates, half-saturation and assimilation efficiency constants, trait-trade-off ‘rules’, etc.); it is primarily focussed on ensuring that empiricists are satisfied that a plankton model labelled as a ‘simulation’ or a ‘DT’ is fit for purpose. To achieve that, set against the complexity of plankton science, we need a vision of how different plankton behave and grow in different environmental settings.

The role of the contributors to this work, as expert witnesses, is akin to the product testers, fault-finding and health-and-safety personnel in a factory. But they are also potential end-users, so they also have an important role in considering the range of potential input and output interfaces.

2. Plankton Simulation Models and Digital Twins

While biologists absolutely do not need to understand the workings of a simulation model in order to validate and/or use a digital twin (any more than one needs to understand exactly how all the parts of a vehicle work in order to drive it), it is beneficial to appreciate what sorts of information are required by modellers, and the constraints under which models are developed and operated. For more information, in the context of building plankton models, see the introductory text of Flynn (2018).

2.1 Key features and components

Simplicity

First and foremost it is necessary to appreciate the strongly divergent form of biological sciences versus simulation modelling. Ecologists typically explore interactions between organisms in the context of food webs; there are 10,000's of plankton species, and a multitude of everchanging environmental scenarios. Modellers have to simplify and thus they have to somehow condense all that plankton biodiversity into very few representative 'boxes' that interact in simplified or exemplar scenarios. The plankton collectives in the model boxes are often labelled as 'plankton functional types' (PFT), or similar, though they often do not align with an ecologist definition of a functional type (Weithoff 2003). Thus, PFTs may be grouped according to an assumed biogeochemical 'role', such as calcification; in reality biogeochemical calcification is an emergent property of the ecophysiology of calcifying organisms and their allied ecologies.

At a simplistic extreme, one could envisage a model containing just a single PFT labelled as 'phytoplankton', with some form of all-encompassing 'loss term' (a closure function) that includes mortality, virus attack, grazing, sinking, DOC release, etc.. In practice, early plankton models more likely contained 1 each of primary producer labelled as 'phytoplankton' and a consumer labelled as 'zooplankton' (e.g., Fasham et al. 1990). Expansions of this format lead to models containing many 'phytoplankton' and a few 'zooplankton' types (e.g., Follows et al. 2007). The descriptions of each of these PFTs are typically very simple, perhaps with an allometric 'rule' to define differences within the 'phytoplankton' and 'zooplankton' types. In the model, 'types' of plankton are defined by the same conceptual equations, just with different values of constant parameters. Typically there will be no virus, no bacteria, no mixoplankton, no age-stage descriptions of ontogeny, no parasites, no resting stages, etc, etc. The abiotic description is usually also much simplified, perhaps limited at the extreme to just nitrate (or 'dissolved inorganic nitrogen') and light as limiting resources.

To a biologist, assuming that they can penetrate the obscurity of the mathematical description in the typical model-focussed research paper, the formulation of the modelling code for each of these PFTs may likely appear as (very) far from being representative of anything living. In the context of the original usage of the PFTs (theoretical studies of ecology, climate change studies, etc.) this may or may not matter. However, for a plankton digital twin it certainly does matter. For any digital twin to be of value, the user must have confidence that it is behaving like a 'twin', under any condition that can be explored in that DT. A plankton digital twin may not likely do everything a real organism can do, but it needs to behave appropriately in a certain set of conditions, to do what it should and, equally important, to not to do what it should not.

Model components

The key parts of a plankton model that align with biology are considered below.

State variables: these are quantities such as nutrient and biomass concentrations. Calculating changes in the value of state variables over time, and especially if they are moved around in a 3D spatial description of the ocean, is very expensive in computational terms. Typically, as far as a modeller is concerned, the fewer the number of state variables the better. The classic Nutrient-Phytoplankton-Zooplankton model (Fasham et al. 1990) describes nutrients, phytoplankton and zooplankton each in terms of just N (e.g. with units of mgN m^{-3}). A biologist, however, is likely to not only expect many parameter descriptors for each organism

(e.g., numeric abundance, age, stoichiometry in terms of C, N, P, Chl, Si, Fe), but also to want an explicit mention of many more types of organisms. Depending on the scenario for application (e.g., flask, mesocosm, estuary, ocean; for digital twin or theoretical exploration), different levels of compromise are required and/or may be deemed as acceptable.

There are other aspects of importance related to state variables. Although numeric abundance is not often modelled, the combination of abundance and biomass provides organism size, which is a key trait affected by, and affecting, various physiological and ecological processes. And while changes in nutrient availability will likely never be as extreme in nature as in laboratory batch cultures, many physiological interactions are impacted by subtle changes in nutrient availability (release of DOC, exploitation of different nutrient resources, toxin production, stoichiometric ecology, etc.).

Constants: these parameters, held constant during a given simulation, define features such as the maximum growth rate at a given reference temperature, minimum and maximum prey size, and assimilation efficiency. Many, if not most, of these values are in reality not even 'constant' for a short period of time. Nonetheless, they are used to help define the operational envelope of the plankton description. For example, the current value of a plankton's N:C or Chl:C stoichiometry must be held within plausible bounds which are defined by constants.

Constants are often 'tuned' by modellers in an attempt to achieve a model output that more closely aligns with data, a process some term as 'optimisation'. In doing so, there is a risk that the values of constants become implausible from a biological view point. This may happen in part because there are few exemplar ranges of suitable values of 'constants' (other than for elemental ratios) that a modeller can reference. In a plankton digital twin, the user may likely wish to experiment with using different values for these 'constants'.

Conceptual structure: this defines how the values of the state variables and constants are brought together, via equations that define interactions and aspects such as rate processes, nutritional state, prey preference etc. Collectively the equations that provide the conceptual structure make the model behave in a particular fashion. The complexity of the conceptual structure is strongly affected by the number of state variables used for each plankton type. For example, it has taken many decades for plankton modellers to move away from assuming fixed Redfield-like ratios of C:N:P; this is despite evidence for variable C:N:P (Geider & LaRoche 2002; Cunningham & John 2017), and overwhelming evidence of the importance of stoichiometric ecology (Sterner & Elser 2002; Mitra & Flynn 2005, Flynn 2010).

The conceptual structure used to describe the physiological functioning of most plankton models is linear; that is to say that very simple equations are used to define rate processes, with no feedback controls regulating, for example, the maximum potential resource acquisition (i.e., ' V_{max} ') to resource satiation. This represents a major departure from how organismal biology actually works. Feedbacks modulating homeostasis are critical features of real organisms, responsible for every single aspect of physiology and behaviour. It is quite possible to construct plankton models with feedback modulations, but most modellers do not exploit the approach. As a branch of modelling called '*system dynamics*' such feedback modulations are widely used in industry and process control. Plankton modellers may not exploit this approach in part because they lack the information and guidance to do so. Others may view these feedback modulations as unnecessary complications. These topics are considered further by Flynn & Mitra (2023).

Some approaches exploited in plankton models provide work-arounds in the conceptual structure which are used by the modeller to provide a pragmatic solution to a complex problem; such approaches may or may not be seen as acceptable by a plankton biologist, and some may be considered as dysfunctional (see **Section 2.5**).

Simulation models and units

Simulation models are usually exploited in dynamic scenarios. Outputs and inputs into the model, and of course features of the modelled subject, typically change over time; a common exception may be simulations of steady-state growth in a chemostat. The model code uses the ever-changing information and, every so many units of simulated time (defined by the integration 'timestep'), it makes new calculations. The longer the timestep, the faster the model can run for the same computational effort. In plankton models, the timestep is typically around ca. 15-30min. This timestep duration is not too dissimilar to the shortest time interval at which a plankton researcher may take samples in a laboratory setting; some experimental methods may yield data at higher temporal resolutions, but many measurements are taken far less frequently (perhaps only daily). The duration of the timestep set against the rate process in reality may mean that certain biological feedbacks may be too rapid to be worth simulating for most plankton digital twins (e.g., energy transients in photosynthesis under flickering light). If sampling of real world data is very infrequent, interpolation is required between sample data points which requires a level of insight by the empiricist. This interpolation can be especially problematic where plankton physiology becomes entrained to a light-dark diel cycle, and yet samples are taken only once a day, perhaps part way through the light phase. To perform such interpolations, and otherwise appreciate the nuances of sparse data again requires the expertise of empiricists.

Simulation models must balance their units. You cannot convert 'cats' into 'dogs'; the organisms, resources and wastes have all to be expressed in the same units (e.g., gC m^{-3}). Where variable stoichiometry is described, each of the interconnected components need to include those units; thus a C,N,P based phytoplankton model would typically be 'eaten' by a C,N,P based zooplankton model; including more elements for variable stoichiometry of each PFT rapidly increases computational costs. This issue of units creates an immediate challenge in the use of laboratory and field data, because so much of empirical plankton science is dominated by measurements of the abundance of the individual (e.g., as numbers L^{-1}), or as chlorophyll. Indeed, very often there are no indications of organism size, let alone of C,N,P content (expressed either per organism, or per volume of water), yet such information is vital for modelling.

A particular challenge exists in describing components of dissolved organic matter (DOM), with respect to their chemical stoichiometry and their concentrations. This challenge for modelling has its parallels in chemical oceanography and in biology (Anderson et al. 2015). Just considering dissolved organic C (DOC), this descriptor may be divided into sugars, polysaccharides, fatty acids, lipids, mucus, cellulose; these are substrates with very different sources and sinks. Is dissolved organic N (DON), which has a similar set of components or varying labilities, to be part of DOC, for example? Or as DOM described as DOM_C and DOM_N to account for changes in the C:N of the DON? And to cap it all, operationally in field studies, DOM typically includes anything that passes through a filter with a $0.2\mu\text{m}$ pore size; that may include viruses, micro-faecal material, even smaller bacteria, and yet it may exclude compounds that may otherwise be categorized as DOM, such as mucus and transparent extracellular polymer (TEP). Such matters need careful consideration during the conceptual stage of building the plankton DT, and also in considering its performance set against a lack of empirical understanding and data. In this respect, the building of a plankton DT forces marine scientists to confront their demons; the problems cannot be ignored because the units have to add up.

Expert judgement can be seen as being required to interpret most experimental results to render the numeric data useful for modelling; this is often needed even in well documented situations with high resolution sampling. Changes in the interpretation of science, with improvements in methodologies over the decades, also complicate the work of the modeller in trying to use historic empirical data series to help configure models.

2.2 Gaps in the data

Modellers typically tune and then validate the behaviour of their numeric model against numeric data. The ideal data set for modelling plankton would describe at least the following (with example units): organism abundance (nos L⁻¹), organisms C,N,P (µg L⁻¹), resource concentrations (C,N,P µg L⁻¹), and waste streams (C,N,P µg L⁻¹). In short, it should be possible to balance the system so that all elements are accounted for over the duration of the simulation. For the simulation, that necessity to balance the system comprises an important test that mathematically the model literally adds up. Very, very few experiments report information to even approaching the level of detail needed to support modelling in this context (e.g., John & Flynn 2002). It is the absence of suitable numeric data series that drives the need for expert witness validation, exploiting phenomenological data, to help provide confidence in the performance of plankton models.

To balance the system, it is especially important to track the fate of non-limiting resources, as the availability of these affects the growth of other organisms later in the simulation. For example, a failure to appropriately describe the assimilation of Si during the diatom-dominated spring bloom may leave sufficient Si in the water column to support an unrealistic secondary bloom of diatoms in the summer (Flynn 2005a). Changes in the efficiency of physiological processes during growth in response to multi-stressors also affect growth dynamics of other plankton. Typically, in experiments, emphasis is placed on the limiting factors; the other factors are most often not even monitored. Thus, in studies of N-physiology, P nutrient will be supplied in excess and not measured leaving us with no idea as to how P-physiology is impacted by N-stress. On the contrary, the classic f/2 growth medium (Guillard & Ryther 1962) contains such a vast excess of N nutrient over that for C and P that phototrophs can readily become co-limited by these other nutrients and/or by the increasing pH that develops during photosynthesis. Such situations create major problems, major gaps in the data and conceptual understanding, that expert witness validation may help resolve. In some instances, these gaps can be profound and only additional method developments will help to resolve them. Most notably perhaps for plankton research this applies to the subject of DOM production, consumption, and allied abiotic-driven transformations.

Understanding the dynamics of changes in the dynamics is also important (e.g., the rate of photo-acclimation with the rate changes in light and nutrient availability during bloom development, or changes in nutrient uptake parameterization with changes in mean ambient nutrient concentrations). A model that can only describe acclimation through to a new quasi-steady-state condition over simulated periods of weeks is of limited use in a dynamic setting. Such a model can generate an output that cannot provide an acceptable simulation (e.g., Flynn et al. 2001). In general terms, perturbation experiments of sufficient duration to capture the dynamics of biological responses, and not (just) steady-state experiments, are of greatest value. Expert interpretation of those data that are available is critical in all of these situations.

2.3 Biology to model

Each plankton description (each as a sub-model) in a digital twin will describe a generic group of physiologically closely allied organisms (e.g., 'diatoms'), or perhaps a tighter group (e.g., 'mixotrophic ciliates'), even down to a species. Many models claim to describe plankton 'functional types' (PFT), though the validity of that terminology may be questioned; in ecology, a functional type describes organisms with a similar role in ecology (Weithoff 2003).

Ecological functionality and physiological commonality may, or may not, align closely. For example, diatoms collectively share much of their core physiological features, but differences in their maximum growth rates, variabilities in their C:N:P:Si:Chl stoichiometries, their C:cell and sizes, chain-forming abilities etc. define where and when they will be most successful. The conceptual core for diatom models in digital twins can be the same, but the dynamics of their simulated growth and survival will differ depending on changes in the model parameterisation (i.e., values of constants).

The plankton model for a given functional type needs to be validated. To do so, for each such model we need to establish the traits describing the behaviour of that organism type. For more general descriptions (e.g., 'small chain-forming diatoms'), we may need to rank the importance of traits that we expect to see expressed in the behaviour of the model, or perhaps define a 'rule' of some form, to enable best use to be made of a given computational load.

Each real organism, and each simulated organism (within its functional type description, as appropriate), has facets of its existence that we may describe as related to inputs, outputs, consumption/assimilation, growth, life cycles, death etc. Various of these facets are modulated in reality through (de)repression or behavioural functions that are controlled via feedbacks. For example, just because a cyanobacteria has the genetic coding for nitrogenase does not mean that it always fixes N_2 , and just because a copepod can eat and benefit from toxin-containing dinoflagellates (in low numbers as part of a mixed diet) does not mean that it always does so. Expression of such feedback features, gradually switching traits 'on' and 'off', can be very important factors affecting the outcome of a simulation, just as they are in reality. Establishing how these feedbacks function in reality, what the response curves may be for controlling them, how non-limiting nutrients are handled, how multi-stressor interactions are mitigated, etc, etc., all require expert interpretation of the data and then an expert validation of the model output. It also requires a suitable conceptual core for the plankton model (Flynn & Mitra 2023).

2.4 Validation – the role of the Expert Witness

Validation is critical; this involves checking that the performance of the model accords with reality and hence that it provides a 'simulation' that is true to the meaning of the word. Traditionally in modelling, validation is undertaken by the modeller with reference to numeric data, exploiting various statistical routines. For plankton modelling this is difficult, and for the uninitiated it can also be dangerous with inappropriate interpretations of data, or inappropriate weightings of the importance of different types of data, being made (e.g., Flynn et al. 2018).

In the quest for simplification, many shortcuts have been taken in the construction of plankton models that, for the empirical expert in these organisms, likely renders the model of questionable ability to produce a 'simulation' in anything other than very specific conditions. To be fair to the modellers, as noted above, there are very few numeric data sets that support conceptual development and the rigorous testing of models of plankton. And then there is the great diversity in the plankton, each facet of which the empiricists may claim as being of 'critical importance'.

To even consider referencing model configuration and performance to empirical data also invariably requires the application of various transforms (e.g., transformation of data on organism abundance and size, or of data for chlorophyll concentration, to derive what the model needs as, for example, $mgC\ m^{-3}$). While the pitfalls in the interpretation and transformation are numerous for laboratory data sets, the use of field data is invariably more problematic because of the cross flows of material in and out of study areas and sampling anomalies (patchiness, fragility of some species, etc.).

Expert witness validation (EWV) exploits phenomenological data. These are the data bound within the knowledge gained from experience, that enables an expert to review a manuscript reporting new observations and make a judgement call on whether they think that the results are plausible. This process is itself problematic, because all scientists display a level of (un)conscious bias from their own perceptions, and often their experience stems from studying (perhaps of one physiological feature in great detail) just a few species. Studies of 'laboratory rat' species give rise to factoids and generalities, such as the often-used assumption of a 1:10 prey:predator size ratio (e.g., protistan-zooplankton include many exceptions to that 'rule' - Hansen et al. 1994). And then there is the Dunning-Kruger effect, and group-think, to layer on additional biases in interpretation.

We have to recognise that the fact that we study in detail so few plankton species is in large part because the other species defy ready manipulation in experiments or in culture; this alone flags that we know little with any great detail, especially for temperate-summer species. There is also a temptation to believe numeric data that are published as ‘fact’ rather than, at best, reflecting what happened when those measurements were taken for that particular set of individual organisms, with their (often poorly recorded) physiological histories, and interpretations based on the then extant scientific understanding.

All that said, we also know enough about how physiology and ecology works to judge when data look potentially correct versus certainly wrong. And an important mantra in modelling is that *it is better to be nearly right than absolutely wrong*. The application of EWV to plankton modelling, set against the computational challenges, requires that we establish which trait(s) must be described, which should be described, and equally important, what must not be there, or perhaps what must not be described in a certain fashion.

Because of the emphasis in studying the effects of limiting-factors in biology and ecology research, establishing the side effects on other processes is problematic. However, such an understanding is also essential, not least because of the consequences for aspects of the dynamics. For example, if assimilation efficiency for a consumer decreases at high ingestion rates in the presence of abundant food then, while not affecting the growth of the individual consumer, conversion of prey biomass to predator population biomass decreases. The fate of the (increased) amount of voided material also changes. In consequence, the whole dynamic is radically altered and the results from the (so-called) simulation can be overturned (e.g., Flynn et al. 2021).

2.5 Dysfunctionality

Above all else, EWV is required to ensure that the plankton simulations do not show dysfunctionality (Flynn 2010). *Primary dysfunctionality* is seen when the behaviour of the plankton sub-model itself is aberrant, with the model output projecting events opposite to those that happen in reality. Primary dysfunctionality is relatively easy to locate, by running the plankton model in batch culture scenarios; if required, in the model prey can be supplied as a non-growing resource to isolate the predator behaviour. More problematic is the location of *secondary dysfunctionality*, which may become apparent only when plankton models are connected to form a food web description. Here, inadequacies in individual plankton sub-models prevent other plankton sub-models from behaving as expected. It is for this reason that it is important that experts in a particular organism type also engage in discussions about descriptions of other organisms that are in lower (e.g., sources of nutrition) and high (sources of loss) trophic positions in their respective plankton food webs.

2.6 Building a Test-Kit for Plankton Digital Twins (PDTs)

From the above, it could be argued that the technical demands for a DT are greater than for a simulation. Simulations are typically run by modellers, and any technical run-time problems will likely be recognised and can be handled in an appropriate fashion. A DT is likely to be used by non-modellers, with the potential for entering parameters that push the simulation envelope beyond that originally tested by the programmes creator. An analogy would be that a modeller using a simulation is akin to a test pilot (alive to potential problems and how to handle them), while the user of a DT is akin to a regular commercial pilot, or even a novice pilot. For climate change science, and similar applications, such extra technical demands are also justified for non-DT models claiming to provide simulations. Just as for statistical modelling, great care must be taken in extrapolating results beyond the operation envelope described from past and extant observations. Only using models with a robust core may confidence be placed in the output.

Only a collective effort by several expert witnesses may tease the above issues apart, to establish what ‘reality’ looks like, or perhaps more easily agreed, what is wrong. Such efforts would be best undertaken through the use of a platform with a suitable graphic user interface (GUI); in short a plankton DT platform is

ideal for checking whether the description is working appropriately. Development of the DT can thus be seen as being a cyclic development/testing collaborative exercise undertaken by empiricists and modellers together.

Building a PDT is far from trivial; the interface for the end-user will take significant time and effort to develop. Typically plankton models are run by specialists in computing, perhaps operating largely in a task-and-finish mode for a specific application. Such models are not usually configured to be operated by an expert in the real world who is (deliberately or otherwise) testing the model to destruction, as required in EWW. Accordingly, it makes sense to at least conduct a sanity check on the building blocks during the construction and early test phases of that presumptive PDT before expending the effort in producing the GUI.

To conduct such a sanity check, in the first instance, developers of each plankton functional type require guidance so that they can at least ensure that the plankton simulation model (the simulation engine, so to speak) is itself not dysfunctional. The form of that guidance can take various forms, from a checklist of ranked behavioural traits, examples of traits that are not acceptable, sketch graphs of what one may expect under a given set of conditions, etc, etc. Some examples are shown in **Figs. 1 & 2**.

Referenced research to support these checks is valuable, but it must use exploit information for which the expert witness has high confidence. While an expert may know how to spot a paper that is not as helpful as it first seems, perhaps containing results that science now interprets in a different way, most modellers and data analysts will not possess such a cogent understanding of the subject.

Limiting resource	Primary response	Potential secondary response
Light	[Chl:C & P _{max}]↑, mixotrophy↑	N:C↑, P:C↑, Fe:C↑, diatom Si:C↑, C:cell↓
N	N:C↓, use of alternates ↑, e.g. (NO ₃ , DON, N ₂) mixotrophy↑	P:C↑, diatom Si:C↑, [Chl:C & P _{max}]↓, C:cell↓
P	P:C↓ use of DOP ↑, mixotrophy↑	C:cell↑, diatom Si:C↑, N:C↓, [Chl:C P _{max}]↓
Fe	Fe:C↓, siderophores ↑, mixotrophy↑	P:C↑, diatom Si:C↑, [Chl:C P _{max}]↓, C:cell↓
Si (diatoms)	Si:C↓, thin frustules, short setae	C:cell↑, P:C↑, [Chl:C P _{max}]↓

Fig. 1 Suggested primary and secondary stress responses for phytoplankton. The primary responses typically refer to immediate stoichiometric responses and patterns of (de)repression control through which the organism attempts to compensate for the stress. Mixotrophy here (for phytoplankton) is enabled through osmotrophy, the use of dissolved organic nutrients. The primary responses are those typically measured in experiments; 'side effects', termed here as 'secondary' responses, can have important implications for the drawdown of other nutrients and for predator-prey interactions via stoichiometric ecology.

Fig. 2 Response curves controlling features of grazing and assimilation for planktonic grazers. As shown here, through a series of feedbacks, satiation for growth decreases motility (B), which will decrease encounter and thence capture rate (A), modifies prey selectivity (C), decreases ingestion rate (D), decreases assimilation efficiency (E), and increases voiding (F). The consequence is that the grazer is less likely to encounter its predator (as it is less motile), is more selective but less efficient (more consumed prey-biomass goes to detritus). Most zooplankton models have fixed motility (if described explicitly at all), grazing and assimilation terms. From (Flynn & Mitra 2016).

2.6 Concluding comments

Building plankton simulation models for must start from a sound conceptual understanding of how the real organisms work, and which parts of that functionality has most leverage upon plankton ecophysiology and thence ecology. The core of most extant plankton models is ca. 50yrs old; over the last century there have been major changes in our understanding of physiology and ecology that are not represented in those structures. This is of critical importance because it affects whether experts in the real plankton world can have confidence in the plankton models run in support, especially, of socio-economic and climate change science.

Ironically, the best way to test for those critical features is to perform a sensitivity analysis using a simulation (digital twin -capable) model. Likewise, to simplify plankton models to the extent demanded for Earth System Models (ESM) used in climate change research requires that we have sufficient data to test the models in hindcast mode; in the absence of empirical data, digital twin models can provide synthetic data to help validate predictive ESM models. The digital twins themselves can thus provide a test platform for empiricists, providing for more robust statements of what are critical gaps in our knowledge worthy of priority research.

Modellers and empiricists need each other. Their interactions have been hindered by language and by understanding. There are very few researchers with practical experience of both empirical experimentation and model development, a situation that must surely be lamented. The building of plankton digital twins provides a focus for both sides of marine science to merge their expertise to advance understanding and provided new teaching and management tools.

3. Building Plankton Digital Twins: Scenarios, Inputs and Outputs, and Expectations

This section considers the base configurations required by end-users of plankton digital twins. Although the exact configuration will depend on the intended operational setting, there is a need to consider likely scenarios and input/output requirements.

3.1 Scenarios

Plankton simulation models can be used for many purposes: teaching, pure curiosity (blue-sky research), planning experiment logistics, commercial/management activities, etc. Those interests may have different time lines and different levels of resolution. We may consider the following examples:

- i. Short duration (ca. 2-7d) for perturbation laboratory or shipboard experiments.
- ii. Medium term (1-4wks) for mesocosm experiments or bloom events.
- iii. Long term (months-years) for seasonal successions through to annual events and beyond to climate change considerations.

While (iii) is likely to warrant a relatively low output resolution, (i) and (ii) would likely exploit a finer output resolution, perhaps down to the size of the simulation timestep (typically of ca. 10-30 min). There may also be interest in coupling these scenarios, such as taking samples for short term incubations (perhaps with isotope additions, or fractionations) from mesocosms, or at different times during a plankton succession.

These operational scenarios are also associated with different levels of complexity in the description of the physical environment. Because simulations are by definition time based, dimensions refer to physical space only. A 0D model setting is applicable to studies in fully mixed waters, such as a flask, or a shallow mesocosm. 1D usually considers a depth dimension (z), assuming that adjacent x,y space is the same at a given z. 3D gives the complete x,y,z description. In all but 0D, the dimension can be described at different levels of resolution, either in terms of explicit distance (e.g., m) or a set number of partitions (e.g., depth z is divided into 50 parts, irrespective of the total depth). 3D descriptions may operate at different resolutions described in terms of degrees.

Why does all this matter? – it matters because every space partition, just like the timestep, adds directly to the computational effort required for the physics and chemistry, and thus directly affects (limits) the computational effort available to describe the biology. Scenario (i) is computationally cheap with respect to time and space (likely as 0D). A 1D water column of 50 partitions is 50x more expensive than an equivalent 0D mixed column description. Scenario (iii) can be extremely expensive depending on the range of x,y,z; run times may be many hours or days (using current computing powers) and thus almost by definition exceed a digital-twin operating scenario, as the user is unlikely to sit watching and interacting with the simulation over that time. The more complex the physical description, the less complex can the biological description be for a given computational effort. There is a real problem here because more complex physical systems (for example, associated with small scale patchiness) almost demand more complex biological descriptions.

For various reasons then, most initial efforts in building plankton digital twins are likely to be for scenarios (i) and (ii). While short-term scenarios may be expected to be more detailed than long-term scenarios in many respects, longer term simulations may be expected to require additional details such as changes with ontogeny, and resting stages, such as cysts. Describing ontogeny is uncommon in plankton models and likewise while resting stages are common in reality (especially in coastal and shelf systems), they are rarely included in plankton models.

Studying all of these matters objectively, looking for sensitivities, will tell us which of the myriad of biological options are most important for describing the processes of interest, and thus warrant consideration for inclusion in scenario (iii) digital twins.

3.2 Extending the scenarios; opportunities and challenges

In simulations it is possible to configure test scenarios that would be impossible to consider in reality. For example:

- the perfect and instantaneous organism fractionation described in models contrasts with the slow and poor fractionation of real plankton samples;
- instantaneous exact reporting of independent rate processes;
- feeding consumers with non-growing inert prey to isolate particular activities of interest;
- tracking the transfer of isotopes throughout the ecosystem.

Furthermore, in a suitable digital twin it would be possible to re-wind a simulation timeline, alter various parameters and replay the simulation to explore ‘what-if?’ scenarios. This could be useful in designing and interpreting empirical experiments, to explore how to best fractionate a sample, when to add isotopes in an experiment, etc, etc.

While all of this provides opportunities, it also presents some challenges in comparing model output with empirical data. An example is the very common use of in vivo Chl fluorescence as a surrogate for phototroph biomass; this relationship varies significantly with the nutrient status and photoacclimation of a given phototrophs as well as with maximum Chl:C of that species (Kruskopf & Flynn 2006). Remote sensed colour signals represent additional challenges. Sampling at a single time point during the diel light cycle is another example. By some means it may thus be necessary to recreate the confused real-world signal in a digital twin, by transforming and otherwise manipulating model outputs so that the end-user experiences something more akin to empirical results alongside the synthetic ‘reality’. Adding stochastic components to the plankton components also provides such variability.

In most instances, output resolution will likely be far finer than that possible in real studies. While models produce instantaneous reporting of rate processes with a temporal resolution set by the timestep of the integration, rate measurements in empirical experiments often involve extensive manual manipulations and/or a series of incubations. Again, when comparing model output to real data it is important to remember the disturbances inflicted on the plankton in empirical experimental protocols that likely adversely affect the meaningfulness of the results reported in the literature.

3.3 Expectations and challenging simplicity in models

There is a famous misquote in modelling, that *all models are wrong*; this is attributed to George Box, and refers to statistical models. Most statistical models consider relationships in a very simplistic fashion, with no cause-and-effect linkage. Such models cannot contain any of the structural fidelity of feedback-containing simulation models, and must inevitably be ‘wrong’.

Simulation models contrast greatly with statistical models. If a dynamic numeric model is ‘wrong’, then it should not be used, and it certainly cannot be used to provide a ‘simulation’. The results from many plankton models are reported in the literature as providing ‘simulations’, when there is scant evidence that they provide a description of anything related to reality.

Whether the description of a plankton in a digital twin is fit for purpose depends on how/if the traits in real organisms that are germane to the simulation scenario are described by the model. Typically in models, traits are defined by the values of (very) few, often fixed, parameters. In real organisms, traits are defined either by their absence, or as their presence along some form of continuum. The latter, as a subset of trait possession, often have minimum and maximum values of expression, with the actual operational value being a non-linear function of various factors. For example, the interactions between the use of ammonium, nitrate and N₂-fixation, operate across a continuum from zero to maximum expression controlled by a series of (de)repression signal linked to cellular N-sufficiency. The end points (typically aligned with minimum and maximum expressions) and the form of the response curve defining the expressed trait value, reflecting

(de)repression controls and other interactions, are all important features in reality and for the functioning of the model. Very few plankton models exploit methods to describe such feedbacks (e.g., Flynn et al. 1997; Flynn & Mitra 2023). The feedbacks that epitomise the defining features of living organisms as taught to school children studying biology are absent from the vast bulk of plankton models.

Another potential problem often raised in the development of complex models is the problem of *over-fitting*. Again this is an issue related primarily to statistical (curve-fitting) models, where a complex curve form that fits through an example set of data (such as a multi-level polynomial, with many constant parameters in its description) is incapable of fitting another data set satisfactorily. In numeric models where the behaviours of individual subcomponents (here as facets of plankton physiology) are modulated by feedbacks, the output may be largely insensitive to the exact values of constant parameters controlling those feedbacks (e.g., Fasham et al. 2006).

The expert witness need not overly concern themselves with the challenge of how to describe the complexities of reality in models; suffice as to say that it is quite possible to describe, for example, cascades of (de)repression and behavioural interactions relating to stress mitigation (Flynn & Mitra 2023). However, as noted earlier, there are good reasons to refrain from proliferating complexities in the model. It is thus important to prioritise the inclusion of trait descriptions (both what to include and how to include it), and to ensure that what is included does not display primary or secondary dysfunctionality (Flynn 2005b, 2010).

The more detailed is our description of plankton biodiversity, the more complex the overall description becomes as each plankton type carries its own traits (size, growth rate potential, resource acquisition modes, motility, vertical migration, etc.) defining its functionality. Again, there is the conflict between biology, driven by its search for, and explanations for, differences between organisms, and the pragmatism of modelling which is constrained by the need to minimise complexity. The resolution to this conflict is to identify what really matters, those traits descriptions upon which the model output is particularly sensitive. That arguably requires an engineering approach of complex-to-simple, starting from a complex model that is indeed capable of providing an acceptable simulation.

3.4 Inputs and Outputs

What makes a digital twin (DT) different from a standard simulation model is the user interface. A simulation model is in essence just the computational engine; for a digital twin the design of the user interface is as important as the functionality of the engine (assuming the latter is fit for purpose, of course).

The DT interface must receive inputs from the user in formats that are meaningful to them, and produce outputs, in appropriate formats, that meet expectations and requirements. Developing the interface requires guidance from expert witnesses just as does the configuration of the conceptual core of the simulation engine.

Traditional simulation models require off-line preparation of input data (not least to transform data units to those used by the model), and often to generate outputs that are in units and formats alien to the expectations of an empirical expert. The operation of the traditional plankton simulation is often distant to the user – set up a configuration file, press ‘run’, and return sometime later to collect the output. For a digital twin the experience needs to be more immediate if not de facto instantaneous. At least with current technologies, this most likely makes short-term scenarios, of limited physical complexity, the most obvious initial focus for plankton digital twins.

Determining whether a simulation is fit for purpose, that it is indeed a simulation rather than being dysfunctional, requires some level of interpolation by the expert witness working from sparse often noisy empirical data points to the high frequency, smooth output generated by the model. This also requires some thought as to what types of output information are required of the DT.

4. Project Components

4.1 Tasks

The project, which engaged over 30 experts in empirical plankton science (see **Appendix 2**), comprised 4 tasks. These tasks were actually set in the reverse order to that with which they are reported. The reason for this is to balance engagement by the experts (starting with what they wanted from a digital twin, including the interface) versus the needs of modellers (starting with what is expected/needed vs what is not considered as acceptable). The aim of the project was ultimately to support construction of digital twins, hence the order of the reports.

4.1.1 Building and challenging perceptions (original 'Task 4')

Contributors were asked to respond to a series of questions and statements about plankton modelling. This was configured to provoke a commentary by experts in the field of plankton ecophysiology on facets of the subject that may be considered in models and digital twins. Also included were questions of approaches used by modellers that may or may not have been deemed to be well founded.

4.1.2 Data to support plankton model construction (original 'Task 3')

Contributors were asked to identify laboratory and field data papers that they consider to be exemplars of plankton dynamics to support the validation (numeric or phenomenological) of simulation models. These references were assembled in an Excel database. This database is the only part of the project which continues to be 'live' after the end of the funded project timeline.

4.1.3 Simplicity vs complexity (original 'Task 2')

Contributors were asked to consider, for a given scenario of interest, the level of detail required to satisfy their expectations. The task was centred around the count of state variables (as a critical feature affecting computational cost), working from the simplest scenario of ca. 3 state variables, until a satisfactory level was attained. The aim was to explore how experts would rank the importance of facets of the system of interest when confronted with the realities of limiting computational resources. Also included was a requirement to identify when a critical level of complexity/simplicity was attained that was deemed to be satisfactory.

4.1.4 Core features of plankton digital twins (original 'Task 1')

The underlying aim of this task was to discover what types of interface users of plankton digital twins would require. Contributors were asked to consider the conceptual core of a model, the required ecophysiological and abiotic details, and input/output requests.

4.2 Delivering to the tasks

4.2.1 Contributors

Over 50 experts in empirical (primarily marine) plankton science were invited to join the project. Inclusion of modellers was not requested; only two members of the project (Flynn, as lead, and Thingstad) have a sustained track record in plankton modelling but both also have equally extensive experience in plankton ecophysiology and ecology.

Of the 50+ invited, ultimately 32 joined the project. Their names, ORCID numbers (giving access to their publications) and their expressed interest in different plankton function types, are given in **Appendix 2**.

4.2.2 Contributions to tasks

Separate documents report the outcome from the tasks listed in **Section 4.1** (Flynn et al. 2024a, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d), each co-authored by contributors to that task. Contributions of the project leader (Flynn) to

delivery of each of Tasks 1, 3 and 4 were limited to task design, minor (typographic and cosmetic) editing of inputs from contributors, and analysis.

The numbers of people contributing varied between the tasks, but always gave a coverage across all facets of plankton ecology.

The following table details the contributors to the tasks.

Surname, initials	Task 1	Task 2	Task 3	Task 4
Atkinson A	●	●	●	●
Beardall J	●			●
Berges JA	●			
Boersma M	●		●	●
Bowler C			●	●
Brunet C	●		●	
Calbet A	●			●
Caron D	●			
Dam H	●			●
Glibert P	●			●
Hansen PJ	●			●
Jin P	●			●
Lomas MW	●		●	●
Lønborg C	●	●	●	●
Mayor D	●			
Menden-Deuer S				●
Meyer B	●			
Millette N	●		●	
Mock T	●		●	●
Mulholland M	●	●		
Needham D			●	●
Poulton A	●			
Robinson C	●		●	●
Rokitta S	●	●	●	●
Rost B	●	●		
Saiz E	●			●
Scanlan D	●			
Schmidt K	●	●		●
Sherr E	●	●	●	●
Stoecker DK	●	●	●	●
Svensen C	●			
Thiele S	●	●		●
Thingstad TF	●	●		●
Unrein F	●			
Våge S	●			●

5. Summary of Outcomes

Below are reproduced the executive summaries of each of the tasks. Note that these components are in the reverse order of the Task number; see **Section 4.1** for the explanation.

5.1 Building and challenging perceptions (Flynn et al. 2024a)

Contributors were requested to respond to a series of plankton-specific (33) and general (34) statements and questions relating to the description of plankton in models as might be required for building digital twins. Although not directly emphasised, many of these matters may also be interpreted in the context of traditional extant plankton models. The format of the statements and questions varied, including provocative styles akin to those in a media (TV, radio) interview. For the bulk of the responses, contributors were in agreement.

Complexity in depth is of greater interest than complexity in breadth. Accordingly, digital twins describing rather few plankton types with physiological/behavioural detail were of more interest than models in which many plankton types are described each with little detail. This interest also aligns with that for multi-stressor environments and factors that potentially affect changes in plankton biodiversity. The construction of aspirational plankton digital twins which push the boundaries of empirical understanding are encouraged; examples included interests in dissolved organic matter (DOM) production and exploitation, and the subject of stability in food web dynamics. To deliver to such interests will require significant effort to not only design the simulation engine for the plankton but also the functionality of the graphic user interface.

Failures of aspirational digital twin models due to insufficient detail (as distinct to errors in detail) are not unwelcome, as they flag where more science effort is required. Failures due to simplicity for the sake of simplicity (to minimise computational loads) are considered counterproductive, and arguably dangerous, especially if the user of such information is unaware of the problems because model functionality is described inadequately. The underlying functionality of plankton models needs to be clear. Appropriate use of infographics to explain model functionality to empiricists, rather than relying on mathematical or computer language, is highly desirable. Opportunities to educate empirical plankton scientists in simulation modelling is also required.

Responses to the questions/statements cast doubts upon the functionality of core parts of extant plankton models. By inference (although only raised explicitly in 1 of the 77 questions/statements), doubts are also cast upon the deployment of those plankton simulation models for applied use in, for example, fisheries and biogeochemical circulation models. Having simple plankton models with biodiversity-like descriptors (i.e., species or taxon names) for organisms that are not actually matched by the models functionality give an unjustified level of confidence in simulation projections.

The failure to adequately integrate plankton simulation modelling with empirical plankton research over the last 50 years has resulted in miss-communication and a loss of opportunity for further understanding of plankton communities. The availability of plankton digital twins, available in some form of in silico laboratory, would help promote bi-directional interactions between empiricists and modellers.

5.2 Data to support plankton model construction (Flynn et al. 2024b).

This work includes information to assist contributors in identifying data of use to modellers, including considerations of the types of data that modellers need, and the challenges inherent in certain data types.

Contributors were requested to provide exemplar references that they considered supportive of plankton modelling targeted at developing digital twins. These data were deposited in a database held in an Excel spreadsheet file (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10948648>). The database, containing over 120 entries, can be explored using multi-level sort functions. Although entries contain data dominated by primary producers, temperature, light and inorganic nutrients, there are also a good range of other data types. Data also come from a range of different systems (laboratory, field, batch, steady-state).

Additional contributions are welcome, and the published database will be re-published to make such additions available on open access.

5.3 Simplicity vs complexity (Flynn et al. 2024c)

Nine experts in empirical plankton science contributed to configuring aspirational plankton digital twins (PDT) of different levels of complexity, with emphasis on the required number of state variables. Those state variables could be allocated to any combination of abiotic and biotic components (invariably with units of mass m^{-3}). The contributions were divided between those centred on the microbial loop, phototrophy, or on consumers. Most included multiple plankton functional groups, though two of the nine were essentially autecological models (single bacteria type using a complex description of DOM, or centred on phytoplankton phototrophy).

Key conclusions from this work were:

- i) In general, complexity was expected of the models, with simple models (typifying traditional plankton models) not considered to reflect reality sufficiently to be of use.
- ii) As a trade-off for the allocation of a given number of state variables, a preference was expressed in various models for a greater importance on describing plankton diversity rather than physiological diversity as reflected by variable stoichiometry for each of those plankton types included. While stoichiometric ecology is undoubtedly a powerful driver of trophic dynamics, that is only so if the organisms are there to be described in the first instance. To do full justice, of course, both diversity and variable stoichiometry are required.
- iii) Pragmatically, one could argue that there is no logic in having a complex model if it is not possible to parameterise it; simple models have much to commend them. However, both here and elsewhere in the project, a counter view is expressed that one can learn much from the ultimate failure of a well-founded complex model; complexity in models of plankton should not be avoided simply for want of empirical numeric data.
- iv) As much interest was expressed in the non-plankton components of the system as in the organism descriptions themselves.
- v) From (iii), and from other contributions to this project, early iterations of aspiring digital twin models of plankton would likely be useful containing rather few plankton types (ca. <10) operating in a well-defined multi-stressor scenario.

The exercise was useful not only in revealing different interests but also for the communication experience between the contributors and the task lead. The latter indicates that only through actually attempting to build and deploy plankton digital twins can progress be best made. This is because of the intense modeller-user interaction that is required to produce a useful product.

5.4 Core features of plankton digital twins (Flynn et al. 2024d)

Contributors were asked to configuring aspirational plankton digital twins (PDT). To protect the intellectual property of the contributors, their PDT concepts are not presented. The PDT concepts were analysed with respect to the required abiotic and biotic components and input/output needs.

Most PDT concepts were for short duration (<1mo) laboratory or mesocosm scenarios, some with chemostat-like settings. Field scenarios were 1D (with depth). Most concepts required multiple plankton function types, with host-virus, prey-predator and competition (allelopath) interactions. There was also interest in single organism concepts for photophysiology studies. Concepts included scope for multiple stressor/resource descriptions, most commonly including temperature, light (irradiance, light:dark cycle, with some interests in spectra), and pH/pCO₂. While dissolved inorganics were the most requested nutrient form, over a third expressed interest in detailed dissolved organics (i.e., multiple DOM forms and DOC). Two-way interactions were of interest not only for inorganics (with nutrient regeneration), but also for pH, CO₂/O₂, dissolved organics and the fate of debris (including mortality).

Details of the plankton themselves were invariably expected to include biomass with variable stoichiometry (some including fatty acids), and also numeric abundance (often with explicit allometry). Interests in photopigments were dominated by chlorophyll, with some interest in other pigments such as carotenoids. About a third expressed a requirement for inclusion of allelopaths or toxins.

Almost all expressed a requirement for detailed physiological and/or behavioural descriptions for the plankton, including variable prey or host selectivity. Explicit descriptions of ontogeny and of vertical migration or other depth-linked aspects were also of interest. A few required explicit inclusion of omics-linkages within the PDT.

Input and outputs expectations included an interest in a rewind function during the simulation to facilitate 'what-if?' testing, and multiple time and x,y scatter plot options.

In short, the general expectation for a PDT, or at least for first-generation PDTs, describes an *in silico* laboratory in which a range of plankton types would be described to high levels of detail with respect to physiology and behaviour, in a chemically detailed but dimensionally simple (0D or 1D) setting for short-period incubations.

6. Summary Conclusions

There is a clear appetite for the development and deployment of plankton digital twins expressed by the contributors to this project. A major, arguably the most important, consequence of making such platforms available is to break the silo mentality that has inadvertently developed between plankton modellers and empiricists. While molecular biology, which developed from the 1980's as did the emergence of increasing computer power for modelling, is a subject owned by biologists, the same cannot be said of plankton simulation modelling. The result has been a stagnation in the development of plankton models, with some notable exceptions, and a failure to advance models in keeping with the breadth of plankton empirical science.

An emergent result from this work was the poor regard with which the collaborators may hold extant plankton models. Given that most plankton models date from ecophysiological and ecological concepts and mathematical equations dating back 50 years or so this is perhaps not surprising. That is especially so given the changes in empirical science that have radically changed the face of plankton science over that same period. Cynically, one could draw an analogy between extant plankton ecosystem models and movies ostensibly about historical events. The characters are at best loosely based on real characters; the expected ending may be reached but not necessarily by means that accord with the known facts; yet despite these errors, the movie plot is believed by many to truly reflect reality (Flynn et al. 2024a).

The construction of plankton digital twins, from establishing the conceptual base of the descriptions for each organism type, configuring the abiotic description, through to designing the input/output interface, will engage both empiricists and modellers working together. Indeed, one can but hope that just as the molecular biology revolution saw such a blurring of the siloed roles of 'biochemists', 'geneticists', 'physiologists' and 'ecologists', so too will a revolution in plankton modelling act as a driver for a radical overhaul in plankton science.

The test for that development will be the appearance of fully integrated conferences, which will no longer see either the biology or the modelling components shunted to a small time slot in the overall proceedings. To achieve that end, we need to bring modelling and empirical aspects together in education. Simulation modelling needs to become mainstream for ecologists, just as has molecular biology. For sure, digital twins of laboratories, mesocosms and natural systems have a pivotal role in that development. We need to start that journey with due haste because we need simulation models of ecology that we can all have confidence in; they provide us with the only means to gaze into the future and, hopefully, act accordingly.

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Appendix 1: Plankton Digital Twins – analogy to the flight simulator

A widely experienced digital twin, available to run on a PC, is the flight simulator. These are available to describe various scenarios:

- different airports, from rough fields to international airports;
- different countries, continents;
- different climate and weather conditions.

Extended versions are used to train real pilots and ground staff in highly complex situations, most are used just for fun as a hobby, some are used to simulate a radio-controlled model aircraft flying in a playing field so that the first real flight does not end in disaster.

Within the flight simulator, there may be different types of aircraft, such as:

- hot-air balloons,
- gliders,
- gyrocopters,
- small and large helicopters,
- multicopter helicopters,
- single and multiple propeller or turboprop aircraft,
- twin through to multiple turbofan aircraft of different types and configuration,

The user may interact with this digital twin at different levels, perhaps as a manager in airport control tower, ground staff, or as pilot in one of the aircraft. The simulator may run with multiple players, each with different roles, or conversely the user could just sit back and watch the cybernetics controlling all the aircraft having first defined the scenario.

Considering the complexity of the aircraft types: the detail with which these are described may vary from:

- very simple (perhaps glider vs helicopter vs fixed-wing aircraft),
- intermediate (for example, differentiating the fixed-wing aircraft according to their size, or powerplant),
- highly detailed (down to the actual manufacturer type designation and detailed control panels).

It is important to note that not only is the flight simulator a digital twin, but every component seen in that simulation is built to a digital twin standard. Whether one considers it to be a good representation depends on how much the user zooms in to look. It also depends on what scenario the flight simulator is describing. If it is based on a simulation of an airport then perhaps aircraft size is more important than dividing the aircraft types according to powerplant, because for take-off and landing all of the fixed-wing aircraft will be operating within a certain speed range. Whether that airport is of Bergen (with large and small helicopters, turboprop, twin and quad-turbofan airliners, and the occasional military jet, all controlled with a complex flight control tower, under sometimes very testing weather conditions), or of a small tropical island (small helicopter, single propeller light aircraft and the occasional small turboprop airliner, all controlled from a small hut with a radio, in calm conditions), will also make a big difference.

Back to plankton digital twins

Plankton come in different types (cf. different aircraft in a flight simulator) and interact in different settings (cf. different airport and geographic setting in a flight simulator). The whole collective of many plankton

within the setting is a digital twin. Each plankton type (to whatever level of detail is required, all the way down to species if required) is itself a digital twin.

The behaviour of the full scenario (e.g., a flask, a mesocosm, a column of water, etc., operating under different weather conditions, etc.), describing some facet of plankton ecology, depends on how believable are each plankton type descriptions. The importance of the behaviour of each plankton digital twin is analogous to the way that a flight simulator is more or less believable (i.e., that it conforms to a 'digital twin') depending on how each aircraft type is described and how closely the user zooms in to look.

Depending on how much one zooms in or out within the ecological scenario, the plankton types may be better merged within more all-encompassing groups; for example, species of ciliate vs protistan-zooplankton vs zooplankton. The analogy with the flight simulator may be Airbus A320 vs regional jet airliner vs jet airliner.

And depending on the interest, some plankton may be more detailed than others; thus there may be a highly detailed copepod description with a rather generic phytoplankton description. The analogy for the flight digital twin is that a simulator focused on a helicopter may merge all fixed-wing aircraft into a few groups according to their physical size and their speed of flight.

Irrespective of the level of detail required, the user can still judge whether the description of the individual components is convincing enough for the simulation to conform to being a digital twin. This is an objective test, of course; depending on the expertise of the person looking at the output, a simulation may be more or less likely to be considered as a digital twin. Even so, from a distance most people will likely know enough about the behaviour of different aircraft types to be able to judge if the 'multi-rotor helicopter' is actually behaving like a jet airliner. Likewise, a marine scientist should be able to judge whether a 'diatom' is behaving like a diatom and not like a *Prochlorococcus*. 'Behaving' in the context of plankton includes what it is taking from its environment, what it is putting out, who is eating it, etc. etc.

This project is concerned with ensuring that plankton models intended for digital twin applications are themselves of a digital twin standard. That standard will inevitably depend on the application as that will define how much detail is required of each plankton type description. The more the user zooms in, the more the application focuses on a particular organism, and the greater the level of realism and detail that is required. And as the user zooms out, the more consideration is required of what are the critical facets of the organism types that must be retained set against the computational costs.

One feature of plankton digital twins that will, at least to begin with, be distinctly different to that of a flight simulator is the use of avatars. In a plankton digital twin, outputs are most likely to take the form of time and x,y plots, while in a flight simulator the user often sees avatars of aircraft and ground features as well as having dials and other forms of output. Without doubt, the use of avatars in plankton digital twins would add greatly to the user experience, not least because the importance of size will become very clear; phytoplankton alone range in size across a scale similar to a small mouse to a cow.

